

PROJECT TITLE: ERGODESIGN – IMPROVING DIGITAL SKILLS FOR ERGONOMICS AND BIOENGINEERING INNOVATIONS FOR INCLUSIVE HEALTH CARE

Project Acronym: ErgoDesign

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Official website/s: <http://ergodesigner.eu/> & <http://ergodesigner.tu-varna.bg/>

Software/digital tools for design in the health care sector dynamic toolkit software description: AUTODESK MESHMIXER

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Autodesk Meshmixer is free software that has established itself in 3D digital space as a key tool in the final stage of 3D geometry [1]. Although it is completely free and available for download [2], the software is not open source. However, it is fully completed and practically does not need significant improvements. This is evidenced by the last official version of Autodesk from (April, 2018) [3]. Also in the official main page of Autodesk it is announced (September 2021) that the Meshmixer software will not be further developed and in practice the final version remains 3.5.

The Autodesk Meshmixer software has a seamless correlation with Blender software [4]. This allows the digitalization-reality cycle to be a continuous process in the context of the transition from reality to virtuality [5, 6]. In this way, bioengineering and ergonomic designers have the opportunity to digitize a three-dimensional geometry if they need to use real-world examples. Conventional methods of working with 3D software are used, as well as additive technologies (2D and 3D scanners, photogrammetric capturing and measurements). In the same way, if necessary for the real materialization of the developed model/s, it is necessary to create a quality three-dimensional geometry of the digital model/s. In order to print 3D or reproduce through CNC machines, it is necessary for the 3D digital geometry to have solid walls; no shape breaches; to specify the different volumes compared to the additive machines.

The main technical advantages of Autodesk Meshmixer software are the work with advanced sculpting tools and "sewing of the mesh" by automated generation of solid walls along the entire 3D volume of the model. This does not exhaust the functionality of the software, which allows precise definition of the parameters. The software is extremely effective when it is necessary to "clean" the generated mesh due to photogrammetric digitization.

Autodesk Meshmixer has the following main functions [1]:

- *Drag-and-Drop Mesh Mixing;*
- *3D Sculpting and Surface Stamping;*
- *Robust Convert-to-Solid for 3D printing;*
- *3D Patterns & Lattices;*
- *Hollowing (with escape holes);*
- *Branching Support Structures for 3D printing;*
- *Automatic Print Bed Orientation Optimization, Layout & Packing;*
- *Advanced selection tools including brushing, surface-lasso, and constraints;*
- *Remeshing and Mesh Simplification/Reducing;*
- *Mesh Smoothing and Free-Form Deformations;*
- *Hole Filling, Bridging, Boundary Zippering, and Auto-Repair;*
- *Plane Cuts, Mirroring, and Booleans;*
- *Extrusions, Offset Surfaces, and Project-to-Target-Surface;*
- *Interior Tubes & Channels;*
- *Precise 3D Positioning with Pivots;*
- *Automatic Alignment of Surfaces;*
- *3D Measurements;*
- *Stability & Thickness Analysis;*

Autodesk Meshmixer supports the following file formats: *.obj, *.ply, *.stl, *.amf, *.3mf, *.off, *.mix [7].

Based on fast and high-quality work with complex 3D geometric shapes, the software is preferred for developing bioengineering and ergonomic models for healthcare needs [8]. Fig. 1 shows the process of making a leg prosthesis, containing: scanning the healthy problem area, digitization and processing in a computer environment using Autodesk Meshmixer software, generating a complete 3D geometry of the prosthesis and real prototyping (with 3D printing), measurement and finalization with a successful result [9].

Figure 1: Process of making a leg prosthesis [9]

Similar to the model presented in fig. 1, all kinds of models and prototypes can be developed for the needs of healthcare. This is fully ensured by the stability of the software, guaranteeing the quality of development.

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Bibliography

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- [5] <https://aj-tuv.org/index.php/ajtuv/article/view/93>
- [6] <https://aj-tuv.org/index.php/ajtuv/article/view/91>
- [7] <https://help.autodesk.com/view/MSHMXR/2019/ENU/?guid=GUID-D11FDE6E-0279-4909-9B9C-1E115506ED9B>
- [8] <https://www.meshmixer.com/health.html>
- [9] <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1gExokQ9lys&t=282s>

The consortium as whole:

The consortium is responsible for the ErgoDesign project.

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- Networks and ICSTED:
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 - Polish Ergonomics Society, an interdisciplinary organization for the development and popularization of Ergonomics in Poland
 - Inclusion and Innovation Technology Center, representing engineers' and engineering knowledge within the largest Hungarian disability organization
 - ICSTED

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